

Meta-Analysis Approach towards Importance of In-Service Training in Teacher's Professional and Social Development

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Abstract

The paper highlights the significance of in-service training and establishes that its role cannot be denied in a teacher's professional and social development. It plays significant role in enhancing teacher's competencies and improves teacher's teaching skills. Its role is of vital importance in achieving teaching and learning outcomes. In-service teacher training enables teacher to have awareness about the advanced instructional technologies used in the teaching-learning process. This equips teacher with modern teaching tools, enhancing a teacher's efficiency and effectiveness. The in-service teacher training program is a systematic attempt to change teacher's attitudes and beliefs

Key Words

In-service Training,
Professional Development,
Teacher's Improvement

and also bring changes in classroom practices. A teacher undergoes different experiences and practices after joining teaching profession. In-service teacher training improves these experiences and practices. Its role is also of vital importance in developing quality education.

Introduction

Education is an essential component for bringing desired changes in the cultural and social setup of any nation. The teacher has a significant place in any society. Its role is of immense importance in developing the education system which further helps in shaping values and norms of the society. Teacher role is very crucial in creating interest in students to achieve society's aims and goals. It is teacher who sets high expectations for students and guides them to realize this expectation. Without effective teacher teaching and learning process is impossible, therefore teaching is not an easy profession but it is a challenging profession (Lagan, 2001). Only a well prepared and experienced can take responsibility for the nation-building. A well-trained teacher knows his strengths and weaknesses and he continuously improves his skills and abilities. He has optimistic attitudes and plays dignified positive role. Such teacher has broader vision and he delivers knowledge more effectively. Teacher having restricted domain fails in delivering his knowledge more effectively and also fails in achieving teaching goals. In-service training of teacher is essential to have quality education and improve teaching quality (Gautmen, 2001).

Education is a continuous process and it requires a qualified teacher as essential components. Teachers are required to achieve learning goals of the educational process. It is also stated that training during service has significant role in teacher's professional and social development. It is, therefore, necessary to encourage teachers to play an active part in varied programs and also in different informal and formal activities in the teaching-learning process. This will help to review and renew their thinking and actions and it will enhance teacher's commitment to profession and commitment to organization (Evans, 2008).

Teacher's duty is to instill the longings and drive for lifelong learning in their students. It is necessary for a teacher to show keen interest and enthusiasm for continuing professional development and show teacher commitment to his job. Continuous professional development helps teachers in accepting changes and development in the teaching-learning process. Continuous professional development is necessary because it helps in maintaining and enhancing the quality of the teachers. Through professional development, head of various institutions is able to perform their different task in most effective manners (Harris & Sass, 2011).

The term “teacher professionalism” is closely related to the professional development of the teacher. It means to acquire knowledge and skills that help teacher in importing contextual knowledge to students. Professionalism is a key component in the successful teaching and learning process. It makes teacher able to enhance students learning outcomes and achieve educational objective and goals (Lagan, 2001).

Conceptual Frame Work on Teachers Professional Development Activities

Professional development includes all the activities and teacher experiences which are going on in the teaching-learning process formally or informally. Professional development takes place in a challenging learning and teaching environment under condition of dynamic changes. Professional development is the process through which a successful teacher review has teaching and learning skills and knowledge content matter. Professionalism enables a teacher to renew and extend there is changing agent to the moral purposes of teaching. A teacher may be able to acquire and develop critical pedagogy, cortical thinking skills, his ability to assessing and evaluating students' progress. It helps the teacher in acquiring abilities in planning the teaching-learning process in sound manner. It enhances teacher's ability to contact with children, young people and colleague in fruitful way in teaching learning environment (Fullan, 1995).

According to Bradson (2002), the term professional development is interpreted in three distinct indefinite concepts. These concepts are improved practice, engagement, and learning. He argues that teacher professional development deals with all those opportunities and practices that change teacher's thinking and reflecting style in such a way to increase teachers' learning and teaching abilities. Teacher professional development programs have immense importance for teacher and also for effective teaching and learning process. It helps teachers in understanding their strengths and their weaknesses and also provides a base to their knowledge. Professionalism identifies the appropriate support and help teachers in attaining their educational goals. It is very helpful in meeting the educational demands vocational needs of the teachers (Kazmi, Pervez, & Mumtaz, 2011). It is also a learning process for teacher that enhances teacher's professional competencies. It has great significance and values in the professional growth of a teacher. Professional development of teacher indicates that there is a link between professional development of teacher and professionalism. The concept of professionalism has important and significant place in all such practices and policies which are designed for professional development (Segon & Booth, 2010).

Teacher's training during service is a hard topic of discussion and has considerable interest in the education profession. Such type of training for teacher or education may be defined in different meanings and ways. According to Guskey (2002), in-service teacher training program is such type of program which is conduct in a systematic way and which tries to bring systematic changes in the policies and practices outside and inside classroom. The in-service education program also aimed to bring alteration in teacher's beliefs and attitude and also in achieving students' learning and teacher' teaching outcomes (Bradson, 2002). Different activities are taking place inside and outside the classroom rooms. Teacher role in all these activities is crucial and it has positive impact on students' learning outcomes. If teacher receives in-serve training, it may bring useful changes in his attitudes, behavior and his way of teaching skills. The in-service training program consists of all such activities, experiences, and skills that improve teacher's professional and social development. In-service training program for teacher is designed keeping in view teacher's professional and social needs (Collinson & Ono, 2001).

One of the important and basic purposes of in-service training is to equip the individual teacher with modern teaching tools in order to be successful in their profession. They may be able to develop professional knowledge, skills and to develop professionalism. It helps teachers in adopting new situations in their professional life. It also improves teacher's skills and it has a positive influence on teacher's performance and teacher meets the students' needs. This may increase learning outcomes of the student. Different research studies have stated that such programs for serving teachers should be conducted in such way to investigate behavior changes of the teacher and it should also improve the quality of teaching and learning process within the school (Hargreaves & Goodson, 1996).

In-service teacher education molds teacher responsibility to deliver his lectures in the most effective way. When teacher joins teaching profession, he undergoes different experiences and practices. All these experiences and practices are part of in-service teacher training program. In-service teacher training provides a lot of opportunities for teachers to learn information and accomplish different teaching techniques. These techniques are helpful in making a teacher potential and improved his performance. This is a powerful and important factor in motivating teachers. It is considered to be one of the important instruments for developing and improving quality education for different stakeholders and to enhance the effectiveness of teacher (Freidson, (1994). The quality and effectiveness of such training program can be interpreted as delineating the expectation and professional needs of the teachers. It is also helpful in meeting the stipulated educational goals and student learning outcomes. In-service

teacher training programs provide wide range of practices and experiences to different teachers. Planning and conduction of in-service training program for teachers are crucial and has immense importance. Such a program helps teachers to attain the required knowledge and skills and it alter teacher's behavior and attitudes in positive way.

Aim of in-service teacher training for a teacher is to increase the qualities of the teacher which in turn positively and significantly affect teacher's performance and his ability. Harris, & Saas (2001), conducted a research study. The theme of their research study was how in-service teacher training program affect value added services. They concluded in this study that in-service teacher training of the teacher has positive influence over teacher productivity in math class. This study further explored that teachers having more professional and teaching experience was more effective than that teacher with less teaching experience. In 2008, Samupwa studied the effects of in-service teacher training on teacher behavior in the classroom and administrative work activities. It was explored that in-service training program activities have significant effect on teachers behavior in the class and his administrative activities. It was found that there were important and significant changes in teacher's behavior after going through training program. Significant changes were also observed in administrative work activities also. In-service training for teacher is also of immense importance in providing and improving quality education. It enables teacher to acquire skills and update their existing knowledge to influence positively students learning outcomes (Troman, 1996). Teacher role is very crucial in providing quality education and becoming aware of their responsibilities and duties. Different techniques are used to measure quality of training programs whether it is in-service or pre-service. A number of indicators are being applied to define good teacher and these indicators serve as tools to evaluate the effectiveness of in-service training program. In-service training program can further improve roles, capacities and teacher's skills to meet teacher's personal needs and institutional needs. It is realized that only well trained teacher can set teaching goals in better way and organize plans and resources to achieve these educational and teaching goals (Pedler, Boydell, & Burgoyne, 2001).

Effective teachers play a significant role in increasing student academic achievements. They are acquainted with modern teaching methods and are able to impart knowledge in most effective manners. An effective teacher has the ability to provide effective environment which is conducive for teaching and learning and meet student's classroom needs (Hopkins, & Stern, 1996). Such teachers care about the needs and expectation of the student. Teacher training program works as a catalyst which brings significant changes in the behavior and attitude of the teachers. It also redefines teacher role, broaden his vision and increases teachers performance. Teacher training programs whether it may be in-service or pre-service enables teachers to have professional approach towards his profession and deliver their knowledge in systematic and logical way. Such teachers are more effective in delivering their lectures. (Kazmi et al, 2011). Johnson and Sloat (2006) have pointed five phases of in-service teacher program. These phases are instruction, information, guided practices, cording practices and performance. They argued that if in-service teacher training is conducted according to these five phases, it produces positive and significant changes in the behavior and attitudes of teachers. (Linnenbrink & Pintrich, 2002).

Teacher professional development is necessary for effective teaching. It is a continuous process. It creates changes and new understanding within the school environment and enables teachers to show better performance. Professional development means a continuous process that results in learning an increase teacher performance and demands of the institution. In this sense, in-service training enhances professional development of the teachers which further more teacher's teaching techniques, improve content knowledge of the subject, and commitment with gathering the latest information (Holroyd, 2000). It also helps teachers to nourish their students accordingly and fulfill the needs of contemporary society. Teacher development practices develop in teacher a systematic approach towards teaching. It also cultivates and promote relationship within the institution and also with students (Ozga, 1995). Teacher's professional and social development aims in development and improvement of quality of teaching and learning in schools. School provides various opportunities for teachers to increase and improve his professional knowledge and teaching skills in most effective way. It also provides opportunities for reflective practices and teacher can learn effectively through professional training and also from personal experiences. It develops new responsibilities and roles for teacher to ensure his effectiveness in the development of the school (Carrington, & Elkins, 2002).

Professional development of teacher works as a catalyst for school improvements. It increases teacher knowledge about the subject and also improves the standard and quality of the teaching methods. Teacher professional development also has a positive effect on classroom management techniques of the teacher. It also provides a piece of valuable information about the assessment and evaluation process of the student. Professional development enables teacher to use reflective practices techniques in their teaching. Through in-service training programs, teacher is equipped with new knowledge and information and believes about contents, pedagogy, and students learning styles (Ramsey, 2000). Learning content knowledge and different instruction techniques are not enough for effective teaching. Teachers are required to update their belief and theories of teaching and learning

through continuous professional developing training programs. The role of professional development is of immense importance both for teacher and students (Guskey, 2002).

No domain is restricted for teacher professional and social development programs. There is no restricted dimension of teacher professional and social development programs. The different researchers put forward different ideas and concept concerning the dimension of teacher's professional development. However, there are some basic and common components which are necessary for quality teaching. According to Hopkine (1996) there are two strategies which are mainly used to provide better teaching-learning environment in school. First is the ongoing practice in the school and the second strategy is to link and strengthen other internal activities in the school. These strategies are more fruitful when they are provided with pair observation, effective supervision, and in-service training. These dimensions improve teachers study behavior. According to Ali (2004), there are five basic and important characteristic of professional development programs. These are professional development of teacher, professional design,, context of professional development, contents of professional development and the last one is outcomes of professional and social development.

Teacher's professional and social development program aims to build teacher capacities regarding teaching skills and equipped teachers with new concept and skills. It also increases and improves his professional knowledge, skills, and disposition. Teacher professional development programs also emphasis collaboration among different activities and experiences in the school (Fullan. 1995). The performance of schools can be improved if teacher professional development programs are in line with institutional goals and objectives. The purpose and objective of all such development programs is to develop teacher' quality and enhance his skills and knowledge. Different techniques are used to accomplish professional program goals and aims in effective way. It is revealed from different studies that professional development practices have a significant impact on teachers behavior change (Guskey, 2000).

Principles of Continuous Professional Development Programs

Teacher's Continuous professional development refers to any programs which are designed to increase the skills and knowledge of the teacher through orientation, support and training. This development is also likely to positively influence the attitude and approaches of the teachers. It may also result in the development and improvement of teaching learning process in the institution. There are certain principles which are to be observed while conducting continuous professional development programs. These principles are

Awareness of Teachers' Needs

Different researchers are of the view that teacher professional development programs are effective only when teacher's needs are take into consideration Once these needs have been identified, then proper planning should be made to asses and support teachers. Teachers should also be helped in applying the knowledge and teaching techniques most effectively and confidently. If continues development professional programs are planned systematically it will give most fruitful results. If these programs are presented with the idea of increasing personal and professional growth, it will broaden teachers' skills knowledge and result in positive attitude (Guskey, 2002).

Continuous Process

Teacher's professional development programs are always to be a continue one. Continues programs result more successfully as compared to programs which have a short spin of life. Such programs are only successful when they are on continuous basis. Continues developing program generally result in the improvement of quality of education and focus on the enhancement of teacher abilities and his communication skills. Isolated programs of teacher's developments have little values for teachers (Bredeson, 2003).

Diversity of Teaching Programs

Professional development of teachers is also increases by the diversity of teachers in-service training programs keeping in view needs and background. Professional development not only requires the informal learning of teacher but it also gives due importance to teacher's prior knowledge of teachers also a significant role in the successful proceeding are these programs. Potentiality and experiences of the teachers which can be obtained and incorporated into further initiatives and practices also play a significant role in these programs (McEwan, 2001). Acquiring new knowledge and sharing of existing with other teachers is also a crucial factor in the improvement and change in the quality of education system. These programs should not focus on a single side of teacher development but it should focus on the overall development of the teacher. Programs for continues development

must therefore take into consideration this diversity in order to make teacher developing program more effective (Hopcane, 1994).

Clarity of Aims

Before starting any program, it needs clear aims and objectives. Clarity of aims is an essential motivating factor for successful arrangement of teacher developing program. Before starting any training program, organizers and planers of the program set aims and objectives which they want to be achieved through this training program. Most of the teacher do not consider in-service training program as a lifelong process of critical thinking, reflection, and self-direction. Teacher often relay on rote learning of meaningless facts in their preparation for teaching profession. One of the basic purpose of the continuous develop program is to enable and support teacher in providing the best possible instruction so that they become excellent and competent (Bredeson, 2003).

Carefully Designed

Teacher professional and social development training program should be arrange and conduct carefully to meet needs of the teachers and students. Such programs cannot take place in isolation and it needs the collaboration of other related programs. Even the success of best program material or courses are heavily relay on the way how they are used in school as a whole. Successful teacher training programs largely depends upon the implementation of regarding the workshop itself. The aim of such program should be general improvement of the educational system, focusing on critical thinking reflection and self-direction of the teacher (Hopcane, 1994).

Figure 1:

Conclusion

Continuous teacher development is an important issue for any country that has the aim of improving its manpower and capacity building. It is therefore of utmost importance that teacher developing programs should be incorporated into the academic character. It will make aware teacher that there is a need for them to attain professional development programs. Such training programs would assist teachers and they will be more committed to their profession. Teacher development programs could be linked to promotion and a wide range of other incentives. It also helps the teacher in appreciating how they can take benefit from these development training programs. It is argued that teacher way of giving knowledge to students has a direct and significant effect on the performance of students and also on school's performance. It is needed that more teacher professional development program should organized in order to acquire more skills, techniques, and knowledge. This can improve teacher performance.

It is concluded that the continuous professional development of teachers is also beneficial for whole school. Teachers in the school share their existing skills and knowledge with other teachers who may not have the opportunity to attain such development courses. Such programs enable teacher to increase their teaching performance. A teacher who attained these program applies their knowledge and this help in transforming their teaching methodologies in different ways. These programs are helpful in preparing extensive teaching-learning

materials which result in achieving learning objective. In-service teacher training of teachers is also helpful for students. Students are able to seek new teaching style of the teacher and thus understand their lesson bitterly. It is in the interest of the school, students, and teachers that more professional development programs should be planned and organized on regular basis. Every teacher should have participated in these programs regularly.

In-service teacher training programs provide various opportunities that encourage teachers to meet learning objectives effectively. Purpose of in-service teaching training is to pay attention to develop the thinking and pedagogical skills of the teacher. It also develops the management and leadership skills of the teacher. School should concern to the lifelong development of all teachers in order to achieve social aims. Continuous development programs have great importance in teacher education and also in the life of the teacher.

From the extensive review of the literature, it is concluded that continuous development programs are fundamental factors and element in teacher education. It is argued that all teachers should participate in in-service teacher training programs as part of their continuous development. The continuous development program is also helpful in developing the organizational structure and routine work of the school. There are strong demands for teachers to develop and update their professional knowledge and also improve teaching skills continually due to the introduction of new trends in curricula, introduction of ICT and changes in the characteristics of learning needs of the student. Teachers could be introduced to new concept and experiences through in-service teaching training. A teacher could be introduced to new teaching method and instructional technologies. The in-service teacher training program helps teacher in acquiring new skills and teacher can share these skills with his colleagues and also help students. Continuous development programs enable teachers to build their own understanding of what constitutes high-quality teaching to make their own judgment about what should be taught and how it should be delivered.

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